

THE ROLE OF MEDIA LITERACY IN INFORMATION ANALYSIS

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Annotation; In youth from the internet about send skill relevant, court ideological immunity the world, in the global network national information resources raising, age web-inventors thing and spiritual support, this about sites organized different selection, auditions transfer, young people through the rag etc this of the problem efficient the solution be takes _

Key words: media literacy, globalization, internet, media education

AXBOROTNI TAXLIL QILA OLIHDA MEDIASAVODXONLIKNI O’RNI

Annotasiya; Yoshlarda internetdan oqilona foydalanish ko‘nikmasini shakllantirish, ularning mafkuraviy immunitetini mustahkamlash, global tarmoqda milliy axborot resurslarni ko‘paytirish, yosh veb-ixtirochilarni moddiy va ma‘naviy qo‘llab-quvvatlash, bu borada saytlar tomonidan turli tanlov, ko‘rik-tanlovlar o‘tkazish, yoshlarni rag‘batlantirish kabilar mazkur muammoning samarali yechimi bo‘la oladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: mediasavodxonlik, globallashuv, internet, mediata‘lim

РОЛЬ МЕДИАГРАМОТНОСТИ В АНАЛИЗЕ ИНФОРМАЦИИ

Абстрактный; Формирование у молодежи умения рационально пользоваться Интернетом, укрепление их идеологического иммунитета, увеличение национальных информационных ресурсов в глобальной сети, материальная и моральная поддержка молодых веб-изобретателей, в связи с этим проведением различных конкурсов и конкурсов сайтами, поощрение молодежи может стать эффективным решением этой проблемы.

Ключевые слова: медиаграмотность, глобализация, Интернет, медиаобразование.

Today of the day globalization and communication in the environment in young people information analysis do it get, in information about the message to inform, to communicate its direction hidden the meaning right then, short by doing so, har how information analysis to do the eye about teaching all stages belongs to attention focus

it is necessary Developed about others in pedagogy media education personality about from places one in occupation, to media education sure description not given Current daily, media education resources whole in the world wide is being done. Germany in 1982 of UNESCO Grunwald in 1997 in Paris, 2002 in Spain Seville in the city for conferences resolution and in recommendations media education issues belongs to to khtalib passed.

today in the day media literacy Great Britain and Australia humanitarian sciences in the complex as a separate discipline however, in Finland from the mid - 1970s of schools, and since 1977 higher education make it happen study programs about _ And in the 1990s in the country media literacy media education personality with appeared. In Sweden, it is after 1980 education in the process as a separate discipline is taught. _ in Russia in the 1990s media education according to research works take went Pedagogy in 2002 higher education personal for media education specialty according to direction opened., 2005 " Media education " textbook under the auspices of UNESCO was created and Russia film education and media pedagogy site the work dropped. Media literacy belongs to as a science not included Although, our Republic general education media education in schools “History, Literature”, “Motherland” “feeling”, “National independence idea and spirituality” “Basics”, “Informatics” and “Music” subjects to content embedded beam is being taught.

Media literacy is a set of skills that enable people to analyze, evaluate, and create different media forms and messages.

Media literacy allows consumers to analyze what forces media to engage in propaganda, censorship, or bias in information and public programs, as well as to understand structural elements such as media owners and their funding model. In other words, media literacy is the ability to apply critical thinking skills to the messages and symbols transmitted through the media.¹⁹

Media information literacy is creative in action all necessary of them another beam information and through the media efficient get, analyze do, critical on, interpretation do, pass, enter and distribution by will give knowledge, skill, attitude, qualification and practices is a set. today in the day the world popular information on information Choose and right to do topic by being remains. Media literacy, media education, media culture, fake and propaganda information resistance showing is the key of words all two daily seminar training events reflection he cried.

There are different opinions about the concept of media literacy. According to the American International Encyclopedia of Society, "Media literacy" means being active and literate while feeling the responsibility as a citizen in society, being able to accept media texts, it means to be able to create, analyze and evaluate, to be able to understand the socio-cultural and political content of modern media.

¹⁹ Cynthia Vinney. „Very well mind“. What Is Media Literacy? (2022-yil 12-yanvar).

According to S. Firestone, professor of the Royal University of London, media literacy is a movement whose main task is to encourage people to understand, create and evaluate the cultural significance of audiovisual and printed texts.

English political scientist R. Kibey understands media literacy as the transfer of information in various forms, their analysis and evaluation. M. Guetterz says that multimedia literacy includes knowing languages aimed at creating multimedia documents, being able to use devices and methods aimed at processing information, knowing and evaluating new multimedia technologies, and critically accepting media texts.

Media education the student independent thought to conduct, creativity activities to development, information get it, again work, generalize, correct to issue teach the youth worldview, intellectual to do to occur and maturity to find service do of our youth information with performance, information, various lie to information deceived must not stay information separate know, rework, arrangement bring, information content to them, to friends unbiased sources continue, makes sense think takes learning based on information culture is formed of information Who for and what on purpose ownership understand to know important site have one student contact person how technical about for about common to the imagination have to be it is necessary

Education system in front of superior of means one is young to generation modern knowledge.

Giving with together, their independent thinker, universal and national things respectable, high human features have patriot a person as bring up and young people in his mind different ideological children and information attacks against spiritual immunity from the consists of today globalization in the process rejuvenation modern information communication from networks, communication, Internet Go, information analysis reach about knowledge and the eye upgrade important issue.

In the data it is reported that every one user per day from the internet send for many time divide it is that is why today day on demand according to and it is necessary information and data unnecessary and invalid, fake separate get, that is to media literacy have to be necessity come came

Today media literacy is of information why and what for that it is being transmitted to know means - media literate a person to himself information Who and what on purpose created? Ush the message is for me is it necessary - said the question give take and right about release, to him relatively Critical approach take it is necessary

"Media" is from the Latin word "media" - received is "tool", "intermediary" and more more precisely, public information said before the meaning means. Media is

continuous education process visual materials with to enrich, teach good quality passing and students organized appropriation the place about service do.

With that together with modem, photo, video, computer technologies, with the Internet friendship, knowledge for by event.

But the media is good with one as well as service to evil about able. Today the spider to man. the air making himself about shot children in advertisements is being given all to information believer persons, aliens to ideas following going there are others - he says a journalist own thinking for.

First of all, media literacy himself what, why to him today the world across Demand increased about such as to the questions answer to find it is necessary Hard last after information to carry one how many equal to acceleration, development data with one line, help in character of information everywhere to media literacy have to be necessity put.

Traditional so media literacy personalization works be able to analyze and good quality texts after consists of was. So, exactly mother that's it of places event to get information conscious ravish approach today time is a requirement - he said lines Statement done.

Note as we know, globalization, global information society the world In the condition information communication technologies, first of all, Internet children and teens to occur effect doer important to the factor turning around.

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